

THE IMPORTANCES OF MONITORING STUDENTS IN THE CLASSROOM.

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Annotation: This article shows that the careful monitoring of student progress is shown in the literature to be one of the major factors differentiating effective schools and teachers from ineffective ones. Indeed, those analyses which have sought to determine the relative effect sizes of different instructional practices have identified monitoring student progress as a strong predictor of student achievement.

Key words: monitoring, student progress, encouraging, teacher instruction

Student progress monitoring is an important part of education — and it's not just about the students! Regular formal and informal assessments provide teachers with valuable information on the progress and achievements of their students. Not only this, but monitoring student progress also gives teachers the opportunity to reflect on their own teaching and assess the impact of the instructional strategies they use. What are other benefits of student progress monitoring? And how can you assess students in ways that will benefit you both? Our teacher team has got you covered! There are 4 basic benefits for monitoring.

1 Collecting Useful Data

Carrying out regular assessments and collecting student samples of work is a useful way of gathering informative student performance data.

This data is helpful when monitoring the progress of individual students across a range of learning areas, as well as tracking their achievement throughout the year. The data can be used to identify where a student is placed in relation to their personal learning goals, the other students in the class, or other targeted benchmarks. It's also valuable information to share in your parent-teacher communication.

2 Improving Teacher Instruction

One great benefit of monitoring student progress is that it allows the teacher to evaluate the effectiveness of their own teaching. If the majority of the class is

finding it difficult to understand or demonstrate a specific objective, it may not be the ability of the students that is the issue.

You may need to re-evaluate the delivery method through which the concept is being taught. To do this, it is especially important for teachers to assess their own instructional strategies to see if they are working.

A collection of [formative assessments such as exit tickets](#) may indicate that there is a need for the teacher to adjust their instructional strategies to better meet the needs of the students. At times, the need to re-teach a specific lesson may be required — something your [formative assessments](#) will tell you before it's too late!

3 Encouraging Student Growth

Monitoring student progress on a regular basis also enables the teacher to analyze a student's current performance level, as well as evaluate growth throughout a school year.

For example, pre and post-learning tests can measure a student's ability and skill before and after learning new content. Keep them stored safely for quick reference in a binder, and slip work samples and test samples into the folder, recording results as you go.

You can then use the information collected to provide students with valuable feedback about their own progress. With this feedback, students gain greater personal responsibility for their own learning and become more aware of their own academic performance.

4 Enhancing Differentiation Opportunities

Finally, an important benefit of ongoing [monitoring of student progress](#) in the classroom is that the teacher is able to identify students at risk and provide intervention when required. Additional support and instruction can be given to at-risk students and areas that need to be retaught or taught differently can be identified.

Monitoring all students on a regular basis ensures that no student "slips through the cracks" along the way. It also highlights which students require extra help or additional challenges.

Given the strong connection between teachers' monitoring of students' learning progress and those students' academic performance, it would be ideal if teachers received thorough training in monitoring and were highly skilled in classroom monitoring practices. Unfortunately, this is not the case. The research on classroom-level monitoring and assessment reveals that: While standardized achievement test results are the main focus of assessment/evaluation efforts,

nearly all important decisions about student placement, instructional pacing and so on are made on the basis of teachers' ongoing classroom monitoring. Many teachers do not: assign homework frequently or regularly, record completion assignments, monitor seatwork and check on students' progress, or conduct the kind of questioning that helps to monitor learning. Teachers do not receive adequate pre-service training in conducting formal or informal assessments. Administrative support for and inservice training in the skills associated with assessment and monitoring are extremely inadequate. Many teachers are aware that their monitoring skills are inadequate and desire training to expand their capabilities; many others are unaware of the importance of close monitoring of student progress and of their own need for skill development in this area

References:

1. Kurbanovna, A. N. (2024). ISSUES OF LEARNING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AT A HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION. Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, 11(06), 269-270.
2. Aliqulova, M. (2024). АНАЛИЗ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ЯЗЫКА И СТИЛЯ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ АИ КУПРИНА. О 'ЗБЕК TILINING XORIIDA O 'QITILISHI: TA'LIM NAZARIYASI VA AMALIYOTI, 1(01), 82-87.
3. Аликулова, М. Ш. (2023). ЛЕКСИКО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАССКАЗОВ АЛЕКСАНДРА КУПРИНА. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(12 Part 2), 172-174.
4. Bazarova, D. (2024). TA'LIM RUS TILIDA OLIB BORILADIGAN GURUHLARDA "O 'ZBEK TILIDA SO 'Z TARKIBI" MAVZUSINI O 'RGATISH TAJRIBASIDAN. O 'ZBEK TILINING XORIIDA O 'QITILISHI: TA'LIM NAZARIYASI VA AMALIYOTI, 1(01), 88-90.
5. Bazarova, D. B. (2023). ON THE USE OF ALTERNATIVE WORDS. American Journal Of Philological Sciences, 3(05), 48-51.
6. Аликулова, М. М. (2023). ЛЕКАРСТВЕННЫЕ РАСТЕНИЯ РОДА FERULA КАШКАДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ И ИХ ЗАЩИТА ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВОМ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН. Биология и интегративная медицина, (4 (63)), 196-202.
7. Манноновна, А. М. (2022). Лекарственное Поражение Печени И Применение Гепатопротекторов При Этой Патологии. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 3(4), 294-300.
8. Джалолов, Ф. Ф. (2021). Причины низкого усвоения знаний в общеобразовательных средних школах. Среднеевропейский научный вестник», журнал импакт-фактора, 11.

9. ISSN, R. S. A. 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 3, Mar., 2022 Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. ISSN, Rustamova Shahnoza Aripovna, 2776-0979.
10. Rustamova, S. A., & Shaxzoda, S. (2023). THE VALUE OF COMMUNICATION IN STUDENTS FORMING CULTURE HISTORICAL BASES. " GERMANY" MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: ACHIEVEMENTS, INNOVATIONS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS, 9(1).
11. Sh, B. P. (2021). Ideas of Mahmudhoja Behbudi Reflected in Publicism. JournalNX, 7(10), 112-115.
12. Tagayeva, T., & Amanova, S. (2024, April). STYLISTIC PECULIARITIES OF LITERARY TEXT IN CREATIVE WORKS OF BERNARD SHAW. In Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit (pp. 520-524).
13. Tagayeva, T., & Kabridinova, K. (2024, April). INDIVIDUAL FEATURES OF ARTISTIC STYLE OF WM THACKERAY. In Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit (pp. 543-546).
14. Abdullayeva, N. K., & Bakhshilloyeva, N. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS'PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION. Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal, 2(6), 19-28.
15. Shodiyeva, G. (2024). O 'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILIDA SO 'ZLARNI TURKUMLARGA AJRATISH MASALALARI. Interpretation and researches, (4 (26)).
16. qizi Tursunova, M. A., & qizi Shodieva, G. N. (2023). MAIN INFLUENTIAL FACTORS TO LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(3 SPECIAL), 1181-1183.
17. Aliyeva, N., & qizi Shodiyeva, G. N. (2023). Ingliz Tilida So 'Z Turkumlari Tasnifi Masalalari Sharhi. Scholar, 1(13), 22-27.
18. Shodieva, G. (2023). TRANSPOSITION OF WORD CATEGORIES IN UZBEK. Results of National Scientific Research International Journal, 2(4), 40-46.
19. Yusupova, S. A. Z., & kizi Shodieva, G. N. (2023). SOME ASPECTS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(1), 300-304.
20. Tursunova, M., & Qizi, S. G. N. (2023). NAVIGATING ETHICAL DILEMMAS IN BUSINESS DISCOURSE: AN EXPLORATION OF DISCOURSE ETHICS. Science and innovation, 2(Special Issue 5), 687-690.